

**A STUDY ON CHALLENGES FACED BY CUSTOMERS IN PUBLIC
DISTRIBUTION STORES WITH REFERENCE TO THANJAVUR DISTRICT.**

¹Ms.S.Narmadha, ²Ms.A.Monisha, ³Ms.R.Rithika

M.Com student of Bon Secours College For Women(Autonomous),Thanjavur.

ABSTRACT

This study was undertaken to analyze the challenges faced by customers while using the public distribution stores. There are some challenges faced by customers while using the public distribution stores such as poor customer service, Network issues in Biometric, more waiting time in queue etc. The study was conducted in Thanjavur district and the simple random sampling technique was used. The data was collected from 120 respondents by using a google form through structured questionnaire. The percentage analysis and chi-square. The findings stated that the customer face challenges in public distribution stores like biometric and network issues. That the study suggests that they must maintain the biometric system, maintain the queue management system that may increase the customer satisfaction at public distribution stores in Thanjavur District.

Keywords: challenges, public distribution stores, customer satisfaction, Thanjavur District

INTRODUCTION

In Thanjavur district that there are many public distribution stores for the customers they will face several challenges while shopping at public distribution stores. There are some challenges faced by customers while using the public distribution stores such as poor customer service, Network issues in Biometric, more waiting time in queue etc.. However, despite their growth and popularity, customers often encounter various challenges while interacting with these modern retail stores.

This study is understanding the challenges faced by customers in public distribution stores in Thanjavur is essential for several reasons. This study aims to identify and analyze the key challenges encountered by customers in public distribution stores within Thanjavur district. By examining these factors such as product range, pricing, responsiveness, biometric etc.. the study seeks to provide suggestions to improve retail operations and customer satisfaction in Thanjavur District.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- ❖ **Neetu Abey George and Fiona H Micky (2019)¹** conducted a study on the topic ‘The Public Distribution System and Food Security in India’. They researched on the public distribution system in a bird’s eye view. They provided some details on existing corruptions and drawbacks, the majority of their study focussed on some guidelines to overcome the key barriers.
- ❖ **Swapna Shaji and Annie John (2018)²** conducted a study on the topic “The impact of E-POS machines in ration shops. They examined about Post digitalisation satisfaction level of beneficiaries. The outcomes of their study are that the satisfaction level of the beneficiaries haven’t changed after the implementation of E-PoS system.
- ❖ **B. Mahalingam and Akash Raj D P (2016)⁴** conducted a study on the topic “Major draw backs of public distribution system in India”. The key aspect of the study is to analyse major drawbacks of public distribution in the country. The working of system varies regionally with regard to various state governments and union territories, as the study give some crystal-clear image of various demerits and problems associated with the public distribution system.

OBJECTIVE

1. To identify the major challenges faced by customers in public distribution stores in Thanjavur district.
2. To analyse the customer satisfaction level in public distribution stores in Thanjavur district.
3. To provide suggestions for public distribution stores to increase the customer satisfaction level.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study was designed under descriptive research approach. The research methodology used for this study is survey. The data was collected from the customers of public distribution stores through structured questionnaire [google form]. This study was used both primary and secondary data. In this study the simple random sampling was used. The data was collected from 120 respondents. The statistical tool used in this study is chi-square.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTREPRETATION

Table-1 distribution based on gender

PARTICULAR	DISTRIBUTION	PERCENTAGE %
Male	25	21
Female	95	79
Total	120	100

Inference : The above table shows that distribution based upon gender that 79% of respondents are female and 21% of respondents are male.

Table-2 challenges faced in public distribution stores

PARTICULAR	DISTRIBUTION	PERCENTAGE %
yes	65	54
No	55	46
Total	120	100

Inference : The above table shows that distribution based the customer can face challenges in public distribution stores that 56% of respondents are stated yes and 46% of respondents are stated No with their opinion.

Table-3major challenge faced by customers in public distribution stores

PARTICULAR	DISTRIBUTION	PERCENTAGE %
Waiting in queues for long time	10	8
Biometric/Net issues during purchase	55	46
Poor customer service	35	29
lack of responsiveness	20	17
Total	120	100

Inference : The above table shows that distribution challenges faced by customers 46% of customers face Biometric/Net issues during purchase, 29% of customers face Poor customer service,17% of customers face lack of responsiveness,8% of customers face Waiting in queues for long time.

Table-4 satisfaction with the service provided by public distribution stores

PARTICULAR	DISTRIBUTION	PERCENTAGE %
Satisfied	63	53
Dissatisfied	57	47
Total	120	100

Inference : The above table shows that distribution based customer satisfaction with Service provided by public distribution stores 53% of respondents are satisfied and 47% of respondents are dissatisfied with their opinion.

Table-5 chi-square Test: challenges faced in public distribution stores and satisfaction with the service provided by public distribution stores

Null Hypothesis [Ho] : There is no significant relationship between challenges faced by customers and their satisfaction with public distribution stores services.

Alternative Hypothesis [H₁] : There is a significant relationship between challenges faced by customers and their satisfaction with public distribution stores services.

Challenges faced by customers Satisfaction with public Distribution stores services	Yes	No	Column total
	Satisfied	43	22
Dissatisfied	32	23	55
Row total	75	45	120

Expected frequency = [Row total x Column total] or E = [RT x CT /GT]

Expected frequency	Yes	No
Satisfied	41	24.3
Dissatisfied	34.3	21

Chi-square Formula

$$X^2 = \sum(O-E)^2/E$$

Where as,

O = Observed frequency, E = Expected frequency

Observed frequency	Expected frequency	$\Sigma(O-E)^2/E$
43	41	0.09
32	34.3	0.15
22	24.3	0.21
23	21	0.19
	X²	0.64

➤ Degree of freedom $[v] = [r-1] [c-1]$
 $= [2-1] \times [2-1] = 1 \times 1$
 $V = 1$

➤ Calculated value = 0.64

➤ Table value = 3.841

INTREPRETATION

The calculated value of X^2 less than tabulated value thus, the alternative hypothesis $[H_1]$ was rejected. Therefore the null hypothesis $[H_0]$ was accepted that There is no significant relationship between challenges faced by customers and their satisfaction with public distribution stores services.

FINDINGS

The study finds that, There are some challenges faced by customers and the major challenges faced by customer was Biometric/Net issues during purchase that may made the customers to wait in queues for long time. That the study also find that most of the customers are mostly satisfied with the public distribution stores services.

SUGGESTIONS

The study suggests that the public distribution stores must improve the biometric system, maintain the queue management system and have distribute the products to the customers properly these may improve the customer satisfaction levels at public distribution stores at Thanjavur District.

CONCLUSION

That the study conclude that the customers of public distribution stores may have some challenges even though the customers are satisfied with the services and products provided by the public distribution stores at Thanjavur District. The major problem identified is biometric and network issues during the authentication process, which often leads to delays and long waiting queues. Overall, the PDS plays an important role in supplying essential goods to the public, and improving technical facilities such as biometric and network systems can further enhance customer convenience and service efficiency.

REFERENCE

[IJRAR19D2592.pdf](#)

[bing.com/ck/a?!&&p=a56d001401d1afebbc5ef89148a7b547f43df03f065ae8b43a624fa66a2b9c9dJmltdHM9MTc3MzE4NzIwMA&ptn=3&ver=2&hsh=4&fclid=2db4ede4-8403-63e5-2e8d-fb03856162fb&psq=a+study+on+challenges+faced+by+customers+in+public+distribution+stores+review+of+litrature&u=a1aHR0cHM6Ly9pamNydC5vcmcvZG93bm xvYWQucGhwP2ZpbGU9SUpDU1QyMVgwMTg4LnBkZg&ntb=1](https://www.bing.com/ck/a?!&&p=a56d001401d1afebbc5ef89148a7b547f43df03f065ae8b43a624fa66a2b9c9dJmltdHM9MTc3MzE4NzIwMA&ptn=3&ver=2&hsh=4&fclid=2db4ede4-8403-63e5-2e8d-fb03856162fb&psq=a+study+on+challenges+faced+by+customers+in+public+distribution+stores+review+of+litrature&u=a1aHR0cHM6Ly9pamNydC5vcmcvZG93bm xvYWQucGhwP2ZpbGU9SUpDU1QyMVgwMTg4LnBkZg&ntb=1)